

The Role of School Experiences in the Wellbeing of Girls, Special Educational Needs and Low SES Students

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Summary

1. With the current rise in youth wellbeing difficulties, it is important to understand how school experiences contribute to this issue.
2. Based on self-determination theory, this study examines associations between students' autonomy, perceived competence and relatedness at school and their wellbeing.
3. We examine patterns for three student groups with lower wellbeing: girls, students with special educational needs, and low SES students.
4. Data from 2,243 Irish secondary students in second (age 14) and fifth (age 17) year show that students' wellbeing is associated with school belonging and autonomy, but not perceived competence.
5. These links are stronger among low SES students, account for a significant proportion of the gap in wellbeing among students with SEN, but much less of observed gender differences.
6. Results are discussed in the context of the universality claim of self-determination theory and implications for educational policy and practice.

1. Introduction

Young people today report elevated wellbeing and mental health difficulties both in Ireland and internationally. Schools are one of the most important places for supporting youth wellbeing and the impact of school

experiences on children's wellbeing starts early, and continues through second-level education, where several studies point to associations between school engagement and attainment and student's wellbeing. However, it is unclear how students' school lives are associated with their wellbeing. Moreover, some students are particularly vulnerable,

including girls, young people from more deprived backgrounds and those with special educational needs (SEN).

This policy brief summarises a study by Dempsey, Farrell & McCoy (2025) that uses a large sample of Irish secondary school students to test the associations between three affective school experiences (autonomy, relatedness, and perceived competence) and students' wellbeing, while controlling for wider school and student-level characteristics.

2. Theory and Methods

The study applies self-determination theory (SDT) to the school context to consider school factors associated with students' wellbeing. We use student-reported data from 2,243 students recruited from 21 Irish secondary schools, using a stratified sampling strategy (Carroll et al. 2024). We examine whether girls, students with SEN and low SES students differ to other students in (a) mean levels of self-reported wellbeing and (b) the strength of associations between wellbeing and competence, autonomy and belonging. Structural equation modelling is applied to examine the associations, using a multilevel approach to consider variability at the student and school levels.

We hypothesise that girls, students with SEN and low SES students will report lower wellbeing than their peers. Based on self-determination theory's assumption of universal basic psychological needs (Deci & Ryan, 2012), we hypothesise that perceived competence, autonomy and belonging will be associated with wellbeing across all student groups.

3. Results

Results show that belonging and autonomy in the school context, but not perceived competence, are associated with student wellbeing, with belonging being the stronger correlate. This pattern of association was consistent across SEN and non-SEN students, and school context measures accounted for two-thirds of the association between SEN status and wellbeing. The associations between autonomy and belonging and wellbeing were stronger among low SES students than their more affluent peers, challenging the theoretical assumption that all three needs are universal for wellbeing, as posited by SDT (Deci & Ryan, 2012). The results show that belonging and autonomy are more closely related to wellbeing among low SES students whereas competence is more closely related to wellbeing among high SES students. Gender differences in wellbeing were the least accounted for in the models, indicating that other mechanisms not included in the current study are contributing to lower rates of wellbeing among adolescent girls.

4. Policy Implications

A myriad of school-based programmes have been implemented to support wellbeing, with outcomes varying widely. For school practitioners, our findings evidence the importance of promoting student belonging and facilitating their participation in school decision-making as approaches to support student wellbeing. These two approaches may have particular salience for the wellbeing of students experiencing socio-economic inequality and students with SEN.

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Further Information:

Dempsey, C., Farrell, E., & McCoy, S. (2025). Understanding the role of school experiences in the wellbeing of girls, SEN and low SES students: A self-determination theory approach. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 86, 101489. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2025.101489>

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